

Metabolomics and Elucidating the effects of traditional local bioresources on reproductive and productive characteristics in pigs

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Traditional knowledge has been in practice for improving productive and reproductive efficiency in livestock. However, limited hormones and poor ovarian dating enhance the practice of traditional knowledge particularly under backyard pig production systems. Exploring the scientific basis for the used traditional practices can provide new opportunities for the modern pig production systems. Identified locally available bioresources were used *in vitro* as well as *in vivo* for improving reproductive and productive performance in pigs. Metabolomic analysis was carried out for the purpose of identification of composition components in used bioresources. In results, supplementation of locally available bioresources significantly ($p < 0.05$) improved the estimated *in vivo* and *in vitro* characteristics in terms of reproductive and productive performance of the animals. However, no significant ($p > 0.05$) effects of some of the used bioresources were also observed during the study. Metabolomics analysis of the studied bioresources revealed that identified compounds have potential roles as antioxidants, hormonal precursor, antimicrobials, antifungal. Enrichment analysis of the metabolites showed that identified compounds are involved in beta oxidation of long chain fatty acids, glycerolipid metabolism, plasmalogen synthesis and mitochondrial beta oxidation of fatty acids. Some of the compounds have been reported to have role in plasma membrane stabilization and capacitation. In conclusion, the studied bioresources can be used to improve reproductive and productive efficiency in pigs and may be explored further for commercial application.